

CREATIVE APPROACH IN MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN UNIVERSAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10630611>

Abstract. *This article reflects opinions about the management of the educational process in general education schools and the importance of a creative approach. In addition, there will be a debate about the effectiveness of the existence of knowledge about creative approach in the head of the general education school.*

Keywords: *comprehensive schools, creative approach, educational process, educational work, variable education.*

It is known that the school and its educational system and educational work are mainly based on the acmeological direction. However, today's fast-changing education requires a creative approach to the meaningful organization of educational and educational processes in general schools, or to ensure the management of educational work by using it effectively.

We know that education is a person who is ready and able to realize his inner potential in life; a specialist with creative activity; to be able to take care of one's health and lead a healthy lifestyle; along with moral self-determination, it determines how to approach creatively according to the demands of the time. This is done taking into account the interests of students on transpersonal bases - family, school, society, state and personal development interests.

Today, education management is based on new principles. In this process, not restricting and prohibiting, but helping and guiding will help ensure the leadership of the educational institution being managed. Regardless of the type of educational institution, it is for the benefit of both employees and students that it is managed under the leadership of an innovative and creative leader.

The development of a new system or its management in general education institutions can be said to be a feature of today's modern era. Its management can be effective only with the use of modern educational technologies, special attention to subjects, innovative education and educational methods, appropriate organizational structures and forms, economic mechanisms for the development of new ones and their financing, organizational-national forms. It is permissible to focus. This is not a simple matter that can be overlooked. It is here that the topics of management of educational processes in comprehensive schools, creativity-based management processes also emerge.

Currently, intensive research is being conducted for educational systems all over the world. The position of the interests of a more democratic, diversified and efficient society demands it. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, in order to improve the continuous education system, improve the quality of education and ensure its efficiency, instead of material factors, the level and potential of improving the organization and management of educational work in educational institutions is also necessary. In this case, it is necessary to pay special attention to improving the mechanisms of

employees' work and creating the necessary conditions for them to be able to operate in accordance with the requirements of the time.

A creative approach to educational processes in general education schools, based on the organization of management, the need to develop creative abilities of teachers and students allows for the formation of skills that develop under the influence of mutual active relations. This requires ensuring that the educational environment, teaching conditions and methods in general education institutions acquire an interactive character.

We know that creativity (Latin and English "create" means the creative ability of an individual that describes the readiness to produce new ideas and is part of talent as an independent factor). A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities. Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific features, mental sharpness. Also, creativity is reflected as an important factor of talent.

According to the American psychologist P. Torrens, famous in the world of psychology: "Creativity is the promotion of problems or scientific hypotheses; hypothesis testing and modification; identifying the problem based on the formation of decision results; expresses sensitivity to the mutual opposition of knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to a problem."

So, based on the opinion of the psychologist, it can be said that the creative approach is understood as the methods that activate students and encourage them to think independently, and the student is at the center of the educational process. When these methods are used, the teacher invites the learner to participate actively. The learner is involved throughout the process. The benefits of a learner-centered approach include:

- focus on creative work;
- study with higher educational efficiency;
- high motivation of the learner;
- consideration of previously acquired knowledge;
- adaptation of study intensity to the needs of the learner;
- support of the learner's initiative and responsibility;
- learning by doing;
- creation of conditions for two-way feedback.

On the basis of the above-mentioned, it is permissible not to consider any of the following as unimportant in the management of the educational process in general education schools. Because everything in its place appears as a necessary assistant.

The use of new methods and methods of managing the educational process in general education schools based on a creative approach also contributes to the increase in the quality of education and the rapid development of efficiency in this educational institution. In particular, it develops the logical and creative thinking skills of teachers and students, their oral speech becomes more fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is further formed. Also, such methods and didactic games awaken students' passion for learning. Students strive to prepare thoroughly for classes. When they feel that they are a part of the society they live in, they are confident that they will be able to use their skills and talents for the development of their country in the future.

Today, all areas of the life of New Uzbekistan have become a field of deep reforms. In this process, it is impossible not to talk excitedly about the changes in the education system, which is

considered the basis of the social sphere. In recent years, practical work on organizing all stages of the education system based on modern requirements has entered a decisive stage in our country. In particular, there is a social order to develop the creativity of teaching staff in general education schools, and it is demanded to conduct scientific pedagogical research in this regard. In addition, the existence of different opinions in the scientific understanding of the issue of creativity, the fact that no comprehensive conclusion has been reached is another manifestation of the topicality of the topic of the article. Today's modern continuous education system requires a creative approach. In particular, schools, which are the main link of general education, are one of the types of education that leave a deep impression on the life of every child. The managing pedagogue places great responsibility on the teachers. That is, the creative activity of teachers of general education schools still requires special study. Also, the use of methods that determine a high level of efficiency in the management of educational processes in general education schools, or the in-depth study of these methods, also contribute to the efficient organization of educational processes in general education schools, skillful management of organizational processes. will help a lot.

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